

Effect of laser shock peening on the microstructure of GX4CrNi13–4 martensitic stainless steel

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

GX4CrNi13–4

COR13/4

LSP

Laser shock peening

Martensitic steel

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of laser shock peening (LSP) on the microstructure and properties of GX4CrNi13–4 martensitic stainless steel. Three different conditions of surface preparation were examined in this study. First, a control group was left with a ground surface. The two remaining groups were treated with LSP. In one case, a single pass of LSP was applied and in the other case, a double pass of LSP was concerned. The samples were subsequently subjected to corrosion-fatigue testing in a water solution of 0.5 g/l NaCl, metallographic analysis, X-ray diffraction, and microhardness measurements. Experimental results of the corrosion-fatigue test showed that the LSP-treated samples exhibited fatigue cracking at higher force amplitude. Roughness measurements showed that the surface after LSP was rougher compared to the initial ground surface but with a lower proportion of grooves. Greater plastic surface deformation resulted in an increase in microhardness in the near-surface region, which was accompanied by an increase in the calculated density of geometrically necessary dislocations, a decrease in the proportion of retained austenite and coarsening of the martensite phase crystallite.

1. Introduction

Modern hydroelectric power plants have an increasingly dynamic role to play in balancing fluctuations in energy demand. Their ability to rapidly regulate power output by modulating the flow of water through the turbine makes them ideal for grid stabilization. The typical material used to produce the hydroelectric turbine blade components is martensitic stainless steel GX4CrNi13–4 due to its favorable mechanical properties, including high strength and corrosion resistance. These components are exposed to demanding and changing operating conditions that expose them to various degradation mechanisms such as erosion, corrosion, cavitation, and mechanical fatigue due to frequent load changes and associated vibrations [1]. This work focuses on the fatigue aspect of these turbine components.

Fatigue cracks typically initiate at the surface, particularly as a result of pre-existing surface defects, irregularities, or zones of tensile residual stress. To mitigate such damage and enhance fatigue life, surface hardening techniques are employed to improve the mechanical

resilience of turbine components. These techniques aim to introduce or amplify beneficial compressive residual stresses in the surface layer of the material, thereby suppressing crack initiation and slowing crack propagation. To this end, conventional surface hardening methods such as shot peening (SP) [2], hammering [3], and surface rolling [4] are often applied and are often used in conjunction with heat treatment. However, traditional methods have inherent limitations, including uneven hardening, limited penetration depth of the compressive stress layer (typically between 75 and 250 μm), and challenges with precise process control. To overcome these drawbacks, Laser Shock Peening (LSP) has emerged as a more viable alternative [5,6].

LSP typically utilizes high-energy nanosecond laser pulses to induce plasma-driven shock waves that plastically deform the surface and subsurface layers, introducing deep and uniform compressive stresses. Compared to conventional techniques, laser peening offers significantly enhanced control over process parameters, allowing for the targeted placement of peak compressive stresses in critical areas—such as the leading edges of turbine blades or weld fusion zones [7]. Furthermore,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2025.06.002>

Received 21 October 2024; Received in revised form 22 April 2025; Accepted 2 June 2025

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LSP can achieve greater hardening uniformity and significantly deeper impacted zones, with compressive layers reaching depths between 0.5 and 2 mm depending on the material type and specific process parameters [8]. These advantages make LSP an increasingly attractive option for improving the durability and performance of critical turbine components.

A diagram of the LSP process is shown in Fig. 1. A laser pulse with top-hat spatial beam profile is partially absorbed in protective coating (in this case black vinyl tape). This leads to the formation of rapidly expanding high-temperature plasma (>107 K) that absorbs the rest of the laser pulse and exerts a high pressure on its surroundings, forming a shock pressure wave. The pressure generated is further enhanced by confinement water layer on top of the sample (>GPa) [9]. If the Hugoniot elastic limit (HEL) of the material is exceeded, dynamic plastic deformation of the material surface occurs (1) [10]. The heat generated by the laser pulse impact is fully absorbed in the protective coating which makes the deformation purely mechanical in nature.

$$HEL = \left(1 + \frac{\lambda}{2 \cdot \mu}\right) \cdot (\sigma_y + \sigma_0) = \frac{(1 - \nu)}{(1 - 2\nu)} \cdot \sigma_y^{Dyn} \quad (1)$$

where:

μ and λ are Lamé constants; σ_y is yield strength; σ_0 is residual stress; ν is Poisson's ratio; and σ_y^{Dyn} is dynamic yield strength.

This refines the material's grain size and forms subgrains and nanograins, forming a gradient grain structure. This structure is accompanied by a series of lattice defects and increased residual compressive stresses in the surface [11–20]. All these changes can contribute to increasing the fatigue life [21,22] and resistance of the material to stress corrosion cracking [23,24].

In the case of stainless martensitic steel, authors Wang, C. et al. [5] studied the microstructure of AISI 420 stainless steel by TEM observation. They found that due to LSP refinement of martensite laths and M23C6 carbides occur due to dislocation movements in the plastic deformed surface layer. Bhardwaj et al. [25] then found that the number of laser impacts reduces the crystallite sizes of the peened additively manufactured margin steel 300. Rai, A.K. et al. [26] found that multiple impacts increased the depth of peening and nano sub grain formation near the multiple-peened surface. Zhang, Hepeng, et al. [27] observed comparable random texture for peened samples and samples without LSP treatment of 300 M steel, with no specific change in grain size after multiple-pass LSP. However, they observed a transition from high-angle grain boundaries to low-angle grain boundaries with the increasing number of laser passes. Wang, C. et al. [28] and Wang, C., Bian, H., et al. [29] then observed that LSP-treated samples of 420 martensitic steel and 2Cr12NiMoWV steel. Both coincide that after LSP samples had better corrosion resistance in 3.5 % NaCl solution compared to samples without that treatment. Authors explain these better results by carbide decomposition and microstructure nano crystallization which contribute to the formation of Cr-rich passive film with better resistance to the applied corrosive environment. Wang, C. et al. [30] also found that massive LSP treatment tends to improve corrosive fatigue resistance in acidic, neutral, and alkaline NaCl solutions, and the fact that

corrosion fatigue crack growth rate is reduced with increment of pulse energy. Xiong, Y. et al. [31] found that excessive LSP rounds tend to deteriorate the surface roughness and mechanical properties despite increased surface nano crystallization, hardening zone depth, and compressive residual stresses. Pant, B.K. et al. [32] then compared the fatigue life of shot peened with laser shock peened samples of DIN X20Cr13 stainless steel for steam turbine blades. They found that both technologies may have comparable effects on fatigue due to the production of comparable residual surface stresses. Karthik, D. and Swaroop, S. [33] stated that LSP did not affect the presence of delta ferrite particles in the microstructure of 17–4 PH martensitic stainless steel. Li, N. et al. [34] observed an improvement in wear properties and an increase in the microhardness of the 17–4 PH stainless steel cladding layer due to grain refinement and dislocation strengthening effect associated with LSP surface treatment. In another study, Li, N. et al. [35] reported an improvement in wear properties and an increase in the microhardness of the 17–4 PH stainless steel fabricated by wire direct energy deposition technology which was also put in context with grain refinement and dislocation strengthening effect.

The above studies discuss in detail how LSP processing of martensitic steels results in the segmentation and refinement of carbides and refinement of martensite laths due to the movement of dislocations. Moreover, they demonstrate how these transformations, together with the presence of amorphous surface layers, subsequently affect the steel mechanical properties, fatigue and corrosion resistance. In this study, corrosion fatigue tests and microstructural analyses were performed on GX4CrNi13–4 steel samples both with and without LSP treatment. The main objective of the study was to describe, using metallographic analysis, residual stress analysis, and X-ray diffraction analysis, the differences in the material's microstructure and how these differences affected corrosion fatigue.

GX4CrNi13–4 steel belongs to a group of martensitic-austenitic steels. In addition to the martensite and minor carbide phase, it also contains retained austenite, which is possible to find in the form of lamellae between the martensite laths. Residual austenite is a relatively stable phase, but it may undergo martensitic transformation due to external loading. Thus, one of the objectives of this work was also to document the behavior of this phase due to sample surface modification by LSP.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Experimental material

Martensitic stainless steel GX4CrNi13–4 was used as the experimental material. Its chemical composition is possible to find in Table 1.

The experimental material was supplied by ČEZ group a.s., in the form of a cast block, which is commonly used for the production of turbine blades. Prior to the application of the surface treatment, heat treatment by tempering and annealing was carried out to achieve a homogeneous initial microstructure of steel. Quenching was done at 1050 °C, with a 15-h delay and air cooling. Tempering was done at 610 °C, delayed for 18 h and cooled by air. Annealing was done at the temperature of 580 °C and cooled in the furnace.

Samples were manufactured from this block, see Fig. 2, and were divided into three groups: two were LSP treated, and one was left only with the grinded surface. Two different strategies of LSP application were used. The first one was done by one pass of laser shock peening with a power density of 8 GW/cm². For the second one, two passes of laser shock peening with a lower power density of 6 GW/cm² were used. For a surface protection, an ablative layer of black vinyl tape was used in both cases. LSP was done by Bivoj laser in the Hilase center (FZU, Dolní Brežany, CZE), in pulsed mode with a pulse frequency of 10 Hz and wavelength of 1030 nm.

Fig. 1. Principle of LSP.

Table 1
Chemical composition of GX4CrNi13–4 martensitic stainless steel.

[Wt%]	C	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	Fe
GX4CrNi13–4	0.03 ± 0.004	12.3 ± 0.11	4.1 ± 0.02	0.6 ± 0.01	0.7 ± 0.01	0.3 ± 0.02	rest

Fig. 2. (a) Samples shape and LSP treatment application area; (b) The LSP shooting strategy; (c) fixture and specimen storage during the four-point bending fatigue test in flowing water [33].

2.2. Corrosion fatigue test

The corrosion fatigue test was performed using a four-point bending test on a 250 kN Rumul electromagnetic pulsator (*Russenberger Prüfmaschinen AG, Neuhausen am Rheinfall, CHE*). A picture of the test setup is shown in Fig. 2(c). The test specimen was placed so that the notch was oriented in the direction of the applied force. The test specimen was loaded with a set of rollers with a 40 mm pitch. The distance of the supports on which the specimen was placed during the test was 80 mm. The loading frequency was chosen to be 50 Hz. For the corrosion influence assessment, the working part of the specimen was in contact with a 0.5 g/l sodium chloride water solution. The solution temperature during the test was 15 °C. During the test, the test bodies were preloaded with a static force of –2.62 kN. To this force part, a dynamic part of 1 kN was subsequently added. After 2×10^7 loading cycles without specimen failure, the amplitude of the force was gradually increased until a visible crack appeared. As a result, the applied force that caused the crack to form and propagate was found. Metallography analysis was done at the locations where the test specimens cracked during the high-cycle fatigue test, examining both the surface, and the metallographic cross-section.

2.3. Surface analysis

To determine the differences in the roughness profile, Keyence VKX 100 optical profilometer (*Keyence, Mechelen, BE*) was used. The measurement was conducted using a red laser with a wavelength of 658 nm. Images were captured by a $50\times$ objective with a pitch of $0.13\ \mu\text{m}$ in the Z direction. The measurement area was approximately $0.5 \times 3.1\ \text{mm}$. The VK-Viewer software (*Keyence, Mechelen, BE*) was used to collect the data and VK-Analyser software (*Keyence, Mechelen, BE*) was used to analyse the data. The average value of the roughness parameters was calculated from ten measurements across the analysis area, five of which were made in the longitudinal axis relative to the specimen axis and five in the perpendicular direction.

2.4. Microhardness and residual stress analysis

The microhardness testing was done from the surface to the depth of 1.55 mm. The distance between indentations was 0.1 mm. The first indentation was made 0.05 mm from the sample surface. A Struers DuraScan hardness tester (*Struers GmbH, Rožtoky u Prahy, CZE*) was used for this testing. The average values of the microhardness profiles were

compiled from three measurements made on a metallographic section taken in a plane identical to the longitudinal axis of the sample.

The residual stresses were analysed using two methods and in two directions, along the axis of the specimen and perpendicular to it. The residual stresses were measured at the surface using a Rigaku AutoMATE II diffractometer (*Rigaku Holdings Corporation, Tokyo, JP*). The measurements were performed using the $\sin^2\psi$ method in combination with an X-ray cathode Cr with a wavelength $\lambda_{K\alpha 1} = 2.2897\ \text{nm}$. Measurements were performed in the range 146.14° – 165.99° , in combination with a 2 mm diameter apparatus, 30 s exposure time, and 3° angular oscillation. The maximum penetration depth was estimated to be 1–2 μm . The drilling method was chosen to analyse the residual stress profile at greater depths. For this analysis, the Prism device from StressTech (*Stresstech GmbH, Rennerod, DE*) was used in combination with a 1.6 mm diameter drill and 40,000 rpm rotation speed. This analysis was conducted to a depth of 1 mm in 0.05 mm steps.

2.5. X-ray diffraction analysis

X-ray diffraction analysis was performed on a Bruker Advance D8 powder X-ray diffractometer (*Bruker AXS Advanced X-ray Solutions GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany*). A Cu cathode X-ray tube with a wavelength $\lambda_{K\alpha 1} = 0.15405980\ \text{nm}$ and symmetric Bragg-Brentano geometry was used. Due to the size of the examined samples, the irradiated area was circular with a diameter of 1 mm. An Eiger 500 K detector was used to detect the diffracted radiation. The obtained data were then evaluated using HighScore software. After fitting diffraction line and deconvolving the obtained diffraction line, crystallite size and micro-deformation values were calculated.

The measurements of all samples were conducted in an identical manner and identical standards were used for the evaluation so that the measurements made were fully comparable with each other and the results obtained had the correct indicative value. The measurement range was 40 – 102° 2θ . The measurements were conducted at room temperature.

2.6. Metallography analysis

Tescan Mira 3 scanning electron microscope (*TESCAN ORSAY HOLDING, a.s., Brno, CZE*) was used to examine the surface topography and differences in samples microstructure. SEM analysis was performed by SE (secondary electrons) detector, and EBSD (electron backscatter diffraction) detector. The setup for observation was a view field of 25–500 μm , a working distance of 15–20 mm, and an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. EBSD was done using NordlysNano detector with the camera set to 2×1 mode with step size of $0.294\ \mu\text{m}$. Oxford Aztec software was used to collect the EBSD patterns. The collected data were processed using AztecCrystal software 3.1. CarlZeiss Observer Z1m light optical microscope (*Carl Zeiss s.r.o., Prague, CZE*) was also used to capture the samples cross-section microstructure. The measurement was done in bright field mode, with a total magnification $100\times$ – $500\times$. For the structure etching, Beraha II etchant was used, which consisted of 80 ml H_2O , 40 ml HCl , 4.8 g NH_4HF_2 , and 0.1 g $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$. LOM and SEM metallographic images analysis was performed in AxioVision software (*Carl Zeiss s.r.o., Prague, CZE*). For EBSD data capture, Aztec software (*Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK*) was used, and the data were analysed by Channel-5 software (*Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK*). Metallographic analysis was done in the area close to the treated surface of each sample and its middle. A series of 3–15 measurements were done in each of them to get statistically relevant data for evaluating changes in the

sample microstructure.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Corrosion-fatigue test

The corrosion fatigue test results are summarized in the chart in Fig. 3. The comparison of the data shows that the LSP surface treatment resulted in an increase in resistance to dynamic stress of about 50 % compared to the specimens with a ground surface. The specimens that were treated with a single pass of LSP with higher energy in the pulse showed better values compared to the specimens treated with a double pass of laser with lower energy in the pulse.

With higher energy values in the laser pulse, the surface has a more pronounced plastic deformation, which is associated with a significant increase in the residual compressive stresses in the surface layer. These stresses generated by the passing of the laser pulses reach greater depths. They can thus prevent the propagation of fatigue cracks from defects interacting with the surface over a longer time compared to samples with an untreated surface, where tensile residual stresses can act closer to the surface [21]. When using two laser beam passes, lower pulse energy was used, i.e. the plastic deformation of the surface was smaller compared to the one laser beam pass variant with higher energy. The lower corrosion fatigue resistance compared to the single-pass variant can be explained by the fact that the surface deformation was not as pronounced, even though the input energy was sufficient to exceed the HEL limit. Therefore, the structure recrystallization at the sample surface associated with the carbides and martensite laths segmentation may not have been as intense as for the single-pass strategy with the higher pulse energy. This may have resulted in a lower force required to fracture the sample with a surface treated with a two-pass laser pulse strategy in addition to the above, a thin Cr-rich passivation layer could form on the specimen’s surface upon contact with the corrosive environment [28]. This layer prevents the substrate from dissolving and prolongs the incubation time of corrosion damage.

The typical topography of the fractured surfaces is shown in Fig. 4. In most cases, regardless of the surface modification, fatigue crack initiation occurred near the lateral edge of the specimen, see Fig. 4(a-c). From the nucleation zone, the crack propagated near the defect along the boundaries of the prior austenitic grains and then trans-crystalline to the region where a ductile material separation mechanism with dimple

Fig. 4. Comparison of the areas where the test bodies failed in the high-cycle fatigue test. (a-c) Without LSP; (d-f) LSP_1; (g-i) LSP_2; (j) Fatigue crack initiation site- Casting defect; (k) Fatigue crack propagation area; (l) Detail of fatigue crack propagation area.

morphology led to rupture of the test body. Crack initiation occurred in most cases from casting defects that corresponded to or were near the surface or from surface notches caused by mechanical processing of the samples (Fig. 4j). The average size of the fatigue part of the fracture surface was measured for the samples with the LSP_2 group, where it was around $36.8 \pm 4.8 \%$. The size was then around $31.7 \pm 4.1 \%$ for the specimens with ground surface, and $26.1 \pm 4.0 \%$ for the specimens of the LSP_1 group, where a single-pass laser strategy with higher energy in the laser pulse was used to treat the surface.

The authors of the [37] study reported that multiple LSP would increase the number of cycles to fracture and decrease the rate of fatigue crack growth with the number of passes. This is due to the increased level of the applied compressive residual stress in the case of LSP_2 group of specimens, a strategy with lower energy density in the pulse was used against the LSP_1 group of specimens. That led to lower energy of shock wave with energy close to HEL. Thus, microstructural changes associated with plastic deformation of surface such as increase in dislocation density, increased value of pressure residual stresses or nano-recrystallization were not as intense as in case of LSP_1 group of specimens. That is a reason why in corrosion fatigue testing, the fatigue crack growth is faster in case of LSP_2 group of specimens, which led to the failure of the specimens at lower force amplitude values, see Fig. 3.

3.2. Surface analysis

The topography of samples surface is shown in Fig. 5. Fig. 5(a) shows the sample surface after machining. There are mainly traces caused by surface brushing and surface depressions. Fig. 5(b-c) then show the surface after LSP treatment. It is apparent that depressed areas are more prominent on the LSP-treated surface than in case of the initial condition. It can also be noticed that after one pass of LSP with 8 GW/cm^2 , the sample surface appears to be more plastically deformed than the surface after two passes of LSP with the energy of 6 GW/cm^2 .

The change in surface topography observed by SEM was confirmed by surface roughness measurement, see Table 2. These results show the surface roughness value increase in all measured parameters for tested

Fig. 3. Dependence of the force amplitude on the number of cycles to crack initiation [36].

Fig. 5. Sample surface topography. (a) Initial state; (b) LSP_1; (c) LSP_2.

Table 2
Results of roughness measurement.

	Ra [μm]	Rz [μm]	Rp [μm]	Rv [μm]	Grooves area [μm^2]
Initial state	0.439 ± 0.034	6.502 ± 2.817	3.251 ± 2.777	3.252 ± 0.482	
LSP_1	1.488 ± 0.288	11.127 ± 1.478	6.249 ± 0.572	4.878 ± 1.012	
LSP_2	0.821 ± 0.142	9.430 ± 4.084	4.984 ± 3.422	4.446 ± 0.985	
	R _{mr1} [%]	R _{mr2} [%]	Rpk [μm]	Rvk [μm]	
Initial state	7.9 ± 1.8	77.8 ± 1.2	0.277 ± 0.083	1.416 ± 0.164	16
LSP_1	11.4 ± 2.7	92.4 ± 1.8	2.288 ± 0.473	1.019 ± 0.384	4
LSP_2	7.2 ± 3.6	81.1 ± 1.1	0.882 ± 0.533	1.624 ± 0.272	15

LSP strategies. The data also show that one pass LSP roughness profile is a little higher compared to two passes. The increased value of surface roughness profile is a known consequence of LSP treatment [38].

The degree of surface reshaping is affected by several factors. The first is the type of material being treated, i.e., its chemical, phase, and structure composition.

The second factor is the pulse energy and peening strategy, i.e., number of passes or overlaps of surface shots [16,17]. Pulse energy must be high enough to overcome the HEL deformations in the peened surface layer and the surface begins to deform plastically [39]. The third factor is the surface initial roughness and possible defects, such as closed pores closed on the surface and, in the case of LSP without protective coating, surface remelting and oxidation.

Despite their higher roughness value, the post-LSP specimens showed higher resistance in the corrosion fatigue test. As mentioned above, fatigue damage occurs mainly due to surface defects such as grooves, cracks, pores or particle inclusions. The amount and profile of grooves then play a role in fatigue damage to the steel. The area of these

grooves can be determined using the Abbott-Firestone curve, which indicates the material core profile, see ref. [40]. The roughness parameters R_{mr1}, R_{mr2}, R_{pk}, and R_{vk} give the shape of Abbott-Firestone curve. Based on this, the average area of the grooves was determined, see Table 2. The data show that the peening strategy with higher pulse energy in one pass lowered approximately four times the area of grooves compared to both samples without LSP and double pass, low energy pulse LSP. The smaller grooves area also reduces the area in which a crack can be initiated [41]. In addition to the above, the higher resistance of the specimens after LSP was associated with an increase in the residual compressive stresses in the LSP-treated surface layer due to dynamic plastic deformation of the specimen surface.

3.3. Hardness and residual stress analysis

Results of the hardness measurement are summarized in the chart in Fig. 6. The data suggest that the LSP treated sample had higher hardness in the area close to a depth of approx. 150 μm for LSP_2 strategy and 350

Fig. 6. Hardness profile comparison.

µm for LSP_1 strategy. The average hardness in 50 µm depth below the surface was about $288 \pm 21\text{HV}0.01$ for samples without LSP, $310 \pm 16\text{HV}0.01$ for the LSP_1 strategy, and $312 \pm 14\text{HV}0.01$ for the LSP_2 strategy. The difference in the hardness close to the surface could be associated with the higher-pressure residual stresses in this area due to LSP treatment as mentioned in ref. [27, 39] and microstructural changes such as grain size refinement and phase distribution change as mentioned in ref. [20, 22] The results of residual stresses analysis can be found in Fig. 7(a-b).

The data show that for the specimen with a ground surface, the acting residual stresses were around 0 MPa along the specimen axis. In contrast, in the transverse direction, the residual stresses reached a maximum value of -272 MPa at the specimen surface, with a gradual transition to tensile stresses at a depth of 0.4 mm. For the surface of samples LSP_1 and LSP_2, the residual stresses in the longitudinal direction were around -496 MPa and -539 MPa , respectively, and in the perpendicular direction around -461 MPa and -445 MPa .

The highest value in applied residual compressive stresses of -544 MPa was reached for specimen LSP_1 at a depth of 150 µm in the perpendicular direction. For specimen LSP_2, the maximum measured value was -621 MPa at a depth of 100 µm in the longitudinal direction. From the maximum values reached, the compressive stresses gradually decreased with increasing distance from the surface in the case of all LSP-treated specimens.

3.4. X-ray analysis

The X-ray phase analysis was performed with a focus on determining the phase composition and finding relevant crystallographic data of GX4CrNi13–14 steel. The analysis revealed that all the investigated samples contain two basic phases of martensitic steel with a spatially centered cubic lattice - Im-3 m. The main phase is Fe–Cr, and the accompanying phase is $\text{Cr}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_{0.9}$. In addition, the carbide phases Fe_5C_2 and Cr_{23}C_6 are present in the material, but in some cases these phases could not be reliably identified. Fig. 8 shows an overlay of the diffractograms of all measured samples. The exact diffraction lines of standard 00–034-0396 are inserted in the overlay to compare the deviations of the diffraction maxima. Fig. 9 shows an enlarged portion of the overlay of the diffractograms. The chart also shows the exact position of the standard used. The diffractogram of the base material sample (outside the treated area) is not shown in the chart due to its significantly higher intensity. Its value is $44.502^\circ 2\theta$. The magnification shows the asymmetry of the diffraction line of all samples on the right. This asymmetry is caused by the overlap of two diffraction maxima. One is the second $\text{Cr}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_{0.9}$ phase, the other is the Im-3 m crystal lattice identical to the Fe–Cr phase. The slight asymmetry to the left at the base of the diffraction maximum is due to the presence of the carbides Fe_5C_2 (possibly Cr_{23}C_6) phase.

The diffraction maximum for the base material sample is $44.502^\circ 2\theta$. As can be seen from Table 3, the deviations of the diffraction maxima of the individual diffraction maximum do not differ significantly from the material used. However, there is a noticeable increase in the deviation for the affected samples with increasing angle 2θ . This phenomenon

Fig. 7. (a) Comparison of the residual stresses distribution in a direction perpendicular to the specimen axis; (b) Comparison of the residual stresses distribution in a direction longitudinal to the specimen axis.

Fig. 8. Overlay of diffractograms of the sample without LSP treatment affected by grinding (without peening), sample with 1 peening and sample with 2 peening's. The exact diffraction lines of the standard 00–034-0396 are inserted in the overlay to compare the diffraction maxima deviations.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the shift of the strongest diffraction line of the Fe–Cr phase compared to the used standard PDF-2 00–034-0396.

reflects the coarsening of the material.

Table 4 shows the sizes of crystallites (coherently diffracting regions) and their changes. As it can be seen, the base material shows signs of a homogeneous fine-grained structure and minimal variation in crystallite size for the different diffracting planes. For the samples affected by grinding, there is a noticeable increase in the crystallite size of the most strongly diffracting plane (110). At the same time, there is a noticeable difference in crystallite size between the samples depending on the LSP strategy used.

The untreated sample has a crystallite size approximately 6 times larger than the base material. At the same time, this size is 120 [nm] smaller than the sample with one LSP pass and 198 [nm] smaller than the sample with two LSP passes. Thus, the influence of the process is also evident here. The size of the micro deformations inside the crystallographic lattice is only slightly larger for the LSP-treated samples than for the base material. The stresses in the lattice are thus essentially unchanged.

3.5. Metallography analysis

The results of the microstructural analysis by LOM can be found in Fig. 10. It is clear from the data that the structure of all types of samples

Table 3
Observed diffraction maxima of individual diffracting planes and their deviations.

Plane	Standard 00–034–0396	Base material		Without peening		1 peening		2 peening's	
		Position [°2θ]	Deviation [°2θ]	Position [°2θ]	Deviation [°2θ]	Position [°2θ]	Deviation [°2θ]	Position [°2θ]	Deviation [°2θ]
(110)	44.485	44.502	0.017	44.501	0.016	44.483	−0.002	44.536	0.051
(200)	64.779	64.725	−0.054	64.801	0.022	64.745	−0.034	64.635	−0.144
(211)	81.986	81.998	0.012	82.142	0.156	82.046	0.06	81.999	0.013
(220)	98.475	98.528	0.053	98.533	0.058	98.634	0.159	98.553	0.078

Table 4
Crystallite and micro deformation sizes for individual samples.

Plane	Base material		Without peening		1 peening		2 peening's	
	Crystallite [nm]	Microdef. [−]						
(110)	41	0.002	296	0.0023	417	0.0021	494	0.0023
(200)	20	0.0022	51		45	0.0044	92	0.0023
(211)	22	0.0016	63	0.0017	95	0.0022	53	0.0027
(220)	61	0.0018	65	0.0015	27	0.0029	26	0.0029

Fig. 10. Microstructure close to the surface comparison. (a) Initial state; (b) LSP treated sample.

consists of low carbon martensitic lath structure and retained austenite with no specific difference in previous austenitic grain size.

Fig. 11 then shows differences in the microstructure of the samples found during SEM analysis. Light gray particles shown in all images represent particles of retained austenite. The analysis of the amount and size of these particles is summarized in Table 5. The results show that the amount of these particles is almost the same in the area close to the center of samples and decreases near the surface of the samples. The amount of retained austenite in the surface layer was almost identical for samples in the initial condition and in the LSP_2 treatment: about 26 %.

Fig. 11. Typical distribution of the retained austenite particles. (a) Surface, initial state; (b) Surface, LSP_1; (c) Surface, LSP_2; (d) Center, initial state; (e) Center, LSP_1; (f) Center, LSP_2; (RA: retain austenite).

For the LSP_1 treatment, the amount was about 21 %. The retained austenite particles seem a little finer in the surface layer after LSP but their size and shape vary so widely that it can be concluded that the chosen shot peening strategies did not significantly affect the size or shape of this phase. The average fiber length of retained austenite particles was within the range of 586 ± 431 nm.

The lower proportion of retained austenite can be explained by its subsequent transformation to strain-induced martensite. The retained austenite is a structural phase with an FCC lattice with low stacking fault energy [10]. Its stability is influenced by many factors.

These include the size and shape of austenite particles (smaller size increases stability), its chemical composition (the presence of C and N increases phase stability), the temperature gradient, strain and stress rate, and, for example, the tension state at the interface between the structural phases (the tension of martensitic laths increases stability) [42,43]. As the shock wave propagates through the surface of the crystalline material, slip systems are activated and dislocations move. In martensite with a BCC (BCT) lattice, there is a significant increase in the dislocation density and the formation of dislocation sub grains. They are formed when multiple slip systems are activated simultaneously. In those areas there are then new grain boundaries of martensite formed. The high density of dislocations in the martensite laths increases the pressure these laths exert on each other and increases the pressure around the interface between them and the residual austenite regions. This secondary pressure on austenite combined with the shock wave energy can lead to the formation of dislocation twins. At the interface between these mechanical twins and the retained austenite boundary, preferential shear martensitic transformation may occur. The martensitic transformation through this mechanism does not occur in the whole area of the residual austenite, but only at its suitably oriented parts with respect to the pressure wave (deformation). As a result, the residual austenite may disintegrate and its volume fraction at the surface will be lower.

The EBSD analysis was used to evaluate the effect of the LSP on the surface substructure. The results of this analysis are summarized in Fig. 12 and Tables 5–6. Fig. 12 (a–f) shows the crystallographic orientation of the sample surface using Euler and inverse pole figures. It can be deduced from the data that there is a preferred lattice orientation for each surface state. For the initial state and the LSP_1 sample, it was possible to find one orientation maximum in the Z direction with a strong alignment to crystallographic direction (111). For LSP_2 samples, an orientation maximum in the X and Z direction and a slightly lower one in the Y direction was observed. Thus, the results show that after multiple passes of the laser beam, the crystallographic orientation is more randomly distributed than in cases of single pass LSP or initial

Table 5
Results of SEM analysis.

Sample	Area of retained austenite phase [%]		Fiber length of retained austenite phase [nm]		GND density [$10^{14}/m^2$]	
	Surface	Centre	Surface	Centre	Surface	Centre
Initial state	26.1 ± 1.4	32.2 ± 2.3	566 ± 409	826 ± 714	4.0 ± 2.1	2.4 ± 1.4
LSP_1	21.2 ± 2.2	29.6 ± 2.3	499 ± 317	773 ± 580	5.0 ± 2.2	
LSP_2	25.5 ± 2.9	27.4 ± 2.3	591 ± 399	693 ± 492	5.2 ± 2.5	2.3 ± 1.4

Table 6
Grain boundary type distribution.

Grain boundary type	Misorientation angle range	Initial state	LSP_1	LSP_2
Martensite lath boundaries	2°-10°	6.87	21.2	11.2
Martensite packet boundaries (PAGB)	10°-20°	0.41	1.19	0.72
Prior austenite grain boundaries	20°-45°	0.19	0.6	0.23
Martensite packet boundaries	45°-55°	1.17	2.5	1.72
Martensite block boundaries and PAGB	>55°	2.45	5.35	3.24

state. Fig. 12(g-i) then shows the difference in the local curvature in the crystal lattice represented by Kernel Average Misorientation maps (KAM). The local curvature of the lattice can be associated with the dislocation movement and the increase in the density of dislocation on the surface layer. Information about geometrically necessary dislocations density (GND) was thus obtained for the evaluated areas, see Table 3. From the data it can be concluded that the initial dislocation density was about $2.4 \cdot 10^{14}/m^2$ for all three types of samples in the bulk material. In areas close to the surface, the dislocation density was about 2 times higher for both types of LSP-treated samples compared to their central parts and approximately 1.3 times higher than for initial condition samples.

The higher dislocation density in the surface layer of the initial state samples relates to the sample preparation by surface grinding. The LSP treatment then caused a further increase in the density which was slightly higher in the case of the LSP_2 samples. This fact is possibly connected with the second pass of the laser leading to a further increase in density.

The reconstruction and grain boundaries distribution analysis of the surface regions was performed during the microstructure analysis.

In martensitic steels, grain boundaries can be distinguished into the

martensitic lath boundaries, the boundaries of the martensite packets, the boundaries of the martensite blocks, and the boundaries of the original austenitic grains [44]. The proportions of these boundaries for the tested specimens are shown in Table 6.

The presented data show that there was an increase in the proportion of lath martensite boundaries (LAGB) on the surface of the samples after LSP treatment. The increase in their proportion is usually associated with a refinement of their structure and stability due to the accumulation of dislocations in their interfaces. This results in the crack, which was formed during the corrosion-fatigue test, propagating more slowly in the surface region because it is prevented from propagating by the higher density of martensite lath grain boundaries [45]. In addition, in a finer surface structure, the diffusivity of hydrogen from the corrosive environment is more significantly reduced because the grain boundaries act as barriers to its movement, thereby limiting its segregation and reducing the susceptibility of the surface to embrittlement due to hydrogen [46].

The higher accumulation of dislocations around the newly formed grain boundaries led to an increase in the microhardness and applied residual compressive stresses.

The formation of dislocation structures and grain boundaries leads to an increase in the fatigue cracking threshold, see Eq. 2 [47,48] which increases with the value of surface hardness.

$$\Delta K_{th} = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot (HV + 120) \cdot (\sqrt{area})^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where:

ΔK_{th} is the stress intensity factor threshold; HV is the hardness; and \sqrt{area} is the defect area.

The residual compressive stresses acted to greater depths, which in turn led to the reduction of crack development from surface-related defects and thus reduced the ability to develop fatigue failure in the case of the LSP-treated specimens.

The effect of residual stresses on fatigue life can be expressed by Eq. (3) [48].

$$\sigma_f = \sigma_{f0} \cdot \frac{(1 - \sigma_m)}{\sigma_u} \quad (3)$$

where:

σ_f is fatigue limit after LSP; σ_{f0} is fatigue limit free of residual stresses; σ_m is average value of compressive residual stresses on the specimen's surface; and σ_u is the tensile strength of steel matrix.

Eq. (3) above shows that the fatigue limit value increases with the higher value of the applied residual compressive stresses. It then indicates that the LSP surface treatment process had a positive effect on the fatigue limit by increasing the value of the acting residual compressive stresses.

The value of the acting residual compressive stresses could also be positively influenced by transforming retained austenite into martensite. This transformation is accompanied by the development of compressive stresses that increase the fatigue life of the steel microstructure [49].

With the growth of the fatigue crack, plastic deformation of the material occurs in the region in front of the crack tip. If there is a lamella of austenite in this region, then it undergoes local transformation to martensite because of deformation, which is associated with energy

Fig. 12. Results of the EBSD analysis. (a) Euler map: initial state; (b) Euler map: LSP_1; (c) Euler map: LSP_2; (d) IPF: Initial state; (e) IPF: LSP_1; (f) IPF: LSP_2; (g) KAM map: Initial state; (h) KAM map: LSP_1; (i) KAM map: LSP_2.

consumption and closure of the crack tip [50]. This can then slow down the growth of the fatigue crack. On the other hand, the newly formed structure of fresh martensite tends to be brittle and may result in a higher rate of fatigue crack propagation from the interface between the fresh martensite and the initial martensite. In this case, however, the crack development was inhibited in the first stage by the high value of the acting compressive residual stresses induced by the LSP treatment applied to the surface of the specimens.

4. Conclusion

The experiment aimed to verify the influence of the LSP process on the corrosion fatigue and microstructure of GX4CrNi13–4 martensitic steel used in energy industry.

The experiment results indicate that LSP treatment has a positive effect on the corrosion fatigue life of GX4CrNi13–4 martensitic austenitic steel. The results showed that a laser pulse with sufficiently high energy could produce plastic deformation in the surface layer which leads to reduced area of surface grooves- initial points of corrosion-fatigue damage. Another factor that led to the improved corrosion-fatigue life of GX4CrNi13–4 was related to microstructural rearrangement in the area below the plastically deformed surface. There was an observed increase in the values of GND, LAGB, and crystallite size of Fe-BCC and, at the same time, a reduction in retained austenite fraction. These changes indicate that LSP caused a dislocation density increase in the areas close to the surface which further led to the refinement of martensite laths and an increase in microhardness. All these effects contribute to the increase in compressive residual stresses in the surface layer, which prevent fatigue cracks from opening or their initiation on surface defects. This leads to a prolonged time in terms of the corrosion-fatigue damage. In the future, the experiment needs to be supported by TEM analysis of the samples. The results could confirm one of the theses of the study which suggests that there may be a transformation between residual austenite and martensite caused by LSP.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Bricín: Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Zdeněk Jansa:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jan Kaufman:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Zbyněk Špirit:** Investigation. **Zdeněk Fulín:** Investigation. **Josef Strejcius:** Supervision, Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

The authors declare there is no use of generative AI.

Funding

The presented results were obtained using the CICRR infrastructure, which is financially supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports - project LM2023041. The presented work has been realized within Institutional Support by Ministry of Industry and Trade of the Czech Republic. The article was made possible also thanks to the support of CEZ group a.s. This publication was supported by the project Quantum materials for applications in sustainable technologies (QM4ST), funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004572 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. This work was co-funded by European Union and the state budget of the Czech Republic under the project LasApp CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004573.

Declaration of competing interest

All authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this article.

Acknowledgements

This research work was supported by ČEZ Group a.s., which provided experimental material for this work.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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